

Perceptual differences of ERP systems between management and operational end-users

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Abstract

This paper seeks to explore the perceptions of two different user groups - management and operational end-users- on ERP system product performance and post-implementation impact of usage on them. 167 management and operational end-users from 15 manufacturing firms operating in Sri Lanka responded. Over 88 percent of the respondents came from firms that employed more than 500 employees; 68 percent responded that more than 200 employees are using ERP in their firms; 70 percent responded that ERP is in use for more than 3 years in their firms. Significant differences have not been found between the two groups in their perceptions towards ERP system product performance. However, problem solving support, authority and decision rights, and overall performance improvement have been identified as important post-implementation outcomes of ERP usage that discriminate between management and operational end-users.

Key words: Enterprise resource planning systems; ERP product performance; Impact of ERP; User groups

1. Introduction

Enterprise resource planning (ERP) systems represent the latest and most ambitious application of administrative and computer-based technologies in the management information systems. It is an integrated enterprise computing system that lets an enterprise automate the flow of material, information, and financial resources among all functions within the enterprise on a common database, share common data and practices across the enterprise, and produce and access information in a real-time environment (Bingi *et al.* 1999). Hence, according to Lengnick-Hall and Lengnick-Hall (2006) the resulting information network enables four important outcomes: provides a comprehensive information picture that integrates functions, departments, business units and hierarchical levels into a composite, action-response chain of events; provides a single, comprehensive database in which all business transactions are entered, recorded, processed, monitored, and reported; increases the speed of information transactions; and increases structural connectivity across units and activities (p.179-180).

Through these benefits, it offers the potential for seamless functional integration, enhanced leverage of tangible and intangible resources, efficient and flexible supply-chain management, make-to-order manufacturing, and other value creating possibilities (Lengnick-Hall and Lengnick-Hall 2006, p.180).

An enterprise system entails many end-user groups ranging from top management to data entry operators. With the implementation of an enterprise system, organizational change is inevitable and individuals who work in those organizations are affected differently, and consequently, different employment user groups (or cohorts) can have differing experience of the system (Arnold, 2006, Gable *et al.* 2008). As corporations recognize the potential for enterprise systems to deliver strategic impacts, differing experiences of the system by different user groups would be a candidate for research inquiry. Therefore, the importance of evaluating enterprise systems at multiple levels within organisations has been discussed among academics and practitioners (Pinsonneault and Kraemer 1993, Sedera *et al.* 2006, Tallon *et al.* 2000). However, a majority of past enterprise system research studies have attempted to quantify the impact of enterprise systems by analysing data collected from only a single employment user group (see Gable *et al.* 2008). Little past research, however, has attempted to investigate how different user groups view ERP system dimensions and such studies showed significant differences between user groups on how different user groups view system dimensions (e.g. Gable *et al.* 2008, Sedera *et al.* 2004 and 2006). Therefore, scholars have highlighted the importance of understanding how different user groups view system dimensions such as accuracy and timelines (see, for instance, Leider and Elam 1994, Sedera *et al.* 2004, Tallon *et al.* 2000, Thong and Yap 1996) and post-implementation impact on them, such as authority, resource control, and superior and peer visibility (see, for instance, Arnold 2006, Scapens and Jazayeri 2003). Although there are considerable research studies available that attempted to investigate how different user groups view ERP system dimensions (e.g. Sedera *et al.* 2006), systematic attempts to investigate post-implementation impact of ERP usage on individuals have been few (see- Arnold 2006). Such systematic attempts may yield valuable

cross-organisational comparisons of differing perspectives of enterprise systems between user groupings, which are vital in arriving at a holistic view of the enterprise system.

Therefore, the purpose of this paper is to compare possible differences in the perceptions of management and operational end-users on (a) ERP system product performance, and (b) post-implementation impact of ERP usage on them. It is expected that the findings presented in this paper would provide valuable information to academics and practitioners and will be able to establish baseline data that would be a source of general guidance in stimulating future research in this area. Consistent with the objectives, the rest of the paper reviews briefly the theoretical background of the study. This is followed by the methodology adopted. Subsequently, the main findings are presented and discussed. The paper concludes with a discussion on managerial implications of the findings and research areas for further inquiry and understanding.

2. Theoretical background and hypotheses

2.1 ERP system product performance

Several researchers have proposed dimensions to evaluate ERP systems (e.g. DeLone and McLean 1992, Doll and Torkzadeh 1988, Ives *et al.* 1983, Markus *et al.* 2000, Sengupta and Zviran 1997, Somers *et al.* 2003, Wu and Wang 2006). Appendix A summarises some of the frequently used parameters to evaluate product performance. Extant literature suggests that ERP product performance should be evaluated by general employee end-users (e.g. Amoako-Gyampah 2007, Chien and Tsaur 2007, Hong and Kim 2002). Further, it is suggested that the attributes used to measure end-user computing satisfaction, which is defined as the sum of one's feelings and attitudes towards a variety of factors related to the delivery of information products and services, appear to be relevant for an evaluation of enterprise systems (Doll *et al.* 1994).

Bailey and Pearson (1983) first developed a valid and useful measure of user satisfaction (as in Wu and Wang 2006). Since then several researches have been conducted in this area (e.g. Ives *et al.* 1983, Sengupta and Zviran 1997, Somers *et al.* 2003, Wu and Wang 2006). Some of the frequently used measures to evaluate ERP system product performance

include multiple parameters such as reliability (e.g. Doll and Torkzadeh 1988, Sengupta and Zviran 1997), relevance, accuracy (e.g. Wu and Wang 2006, Somers *et al.* 2003), precision (e.g. Ives *et al.* 1983, Sengupta and Zviran 1997), completeness (e.g. Ives *et al.* 1983, Sengupta and Zviran 1997), timeliness (e.g. Doll and Torkzadeh 1988, Somers *et al.* 2003), and output format (e.g. Ives *et al.* 1983, Sengupta and Zviran 1997, Somers *et al.* 2003).

However, there are no agreed measures to evaluate ERP systems (Markus *et al.* 2000). A majority of the studies used only one or two surrogates (e.g. Ang *et al.* 2002, Burns and Turnipseed 1991) while some studies used a global item to measure product performance (e.g. Bendoly and Jacobs 2004).

2.2 The impact of ERP system usage

Technology can play a role of an external agent capable of directly transforming organisations (Dillard and Yuthas 2006, Sun *et al.* 2009). It works as “a mode of organising and perpetuating social relationships, a manifestation of prevalent thought and behaviour patterns, and an instrument for control and domination” (see Dillard and Yuthas 2006, p 203). Hence, there would be considerable impact to individuals subsequent to the implementation of enterprise systems (see Bendoly *et al.* 2006, Bloomfield and Coombs 1992, Jasperson *et al.* 2002, Sewell 1998, Spreitzer 1995, Wilson 1995). Appendix B summarises extant literature that highlights post-implementation impact of information systems. Based on the information provided in Appendix B, following paragraphs describe briefly past studies that highlight post-implementation impact of information systems.

The studies based on the premise that investment in IT alters information processing capabilities of a firm and formal decision making structures theorised and empirically examined the ways in which introduction and use of IT alters exercise and distribution of power (e.g. Astley and Sachdeva 1984, Bloomfield and Coombs 1992, Bradshaw-Cambali and Murray 1991, Jasperson *et al.* 2002, Sillince and Mouakket 1997). In the context of ERP, the integration, standardisation, routinisation, and centralisation that result from the implementation open up opportunities as well as changes within an organisation where identified to influence

exercise and distribution of power (e.g. Astley and Sachdeva 1984, Jaspersen *et al.* 2002, Knox *et al.* 2007).

Further, prior to the implementation of an ERP system, in a functional approach, work is done by various departments independently with very little cross-functional co-ordination (El Amrani *et al.* 2006). However, firms have become increasingly interested in stimulating, facilitating, and maintaining co-operation between the various functional areas (see Bendoly *et al.* 2006; El Amrani *et al.* 2006; Lengnick-Hall and Lengnick-Hall 2006). This calls for a considerable degree of cross-functional co-operation and puts the emphasis on the precedence of processes over functions and users in a new vision of an organisation built around a partition-free horizontal structure and multi-functional work teams (El Amrani *et al.*, 2006). The process orientation of the software promotes greater cross-functional integration and facilitates information sharing across different parts of the organisation (Goodhue *et al.* 1992). Cross-functionality, which stems from cross-functional integration, refers to people awareness of interdependencies and information sharing between various organisational units (see El Amrani *et al.* 2006, Gattiker and Goodhue 2005).

When the ERP system went live, many employees were required to interact with the system to complete their job duties and their focus had to be on the business. These were the employees who previously focused on production, operated on a tightly designed schedule and plan that was provided to them, and did not have to interact with the information system to perform their job (Arnold, 2006). The changes occur with the ERP system implementation require them to utilize the system to initiate, plan, and complete the production process and also enter all relevant information throughout the process. Further, interacting with the system was not optional, because their job could not be performed without that interaction (Arnold, 2006). Hence, the inherent design of ERP tends to give end-users more job discretion than their functional needs (Sia *et al.* 2002, p.25). Several studies investigated the influence of job discretion on end-users and highlight that ERP give them more job discretion than their job needs (e.g. Scapens and Jazayeri 2003, Sia *et al.* 2002, Spears and Lea 1994, Spreitzer 1995). Further, its ability to integrate front-end and back-end operations often results in greater

task concentration by expanding one's job scope. According to Sia *et al.* (2002) "the expanded job scope could make jobs of some employees more significant or 'powerful' than before" (see Sia *et al.* 2002, p.26). Furthermore, it is highlighted that "the process-oriented design expands access to information, allowing employees greater flexibility in doing their jobs and in shifting their work priorities, and also allowing them to make decisions that used to be formally referred upward or to other departments due to lack of information" (Sia *et al.* 2002, p.26). Previous researchers such as Bloomfield and Coombs (1992), Bradshaw-Cambali and Murray (1991), Knox *et al.* (2007) have investigate different aspects of user decision-making with ERP. Some researchers (e.g. Sia *et al.* 2002) highlight that "its ability to breakdown into a sub-domain and redistribute access to a few segregated users based on a strictly 'need to know' basis is limited" (Sia *et al.* 2002, p.26).

Past research also found the implication of new information visibility brought about by ERP on organisational control (e.g. Sewell 1998, Sia *et al.* 2002, Spears and Lea 1994, Wilson 1995). On one hand, as information is captured on a real-time basis and immediately available, users have continuous access to monitor their own performance on an on-going basis (Scapens and Jazayeri 2003, Sia *et al.* 2002). On the other, it provides enhanced visibility to superiors and peers. The single shared database results in data interdependency such that data errors or inconsistencies are glaringly flagged. Hence, the visibility of subordinates' performance is greatly enhanced as management can analyse data in real time, in finer granularity, and also in multiple dimensions (Sia *et al.* 2002, p.25). In addition, users are considerably more visible to their peers (see Sewell 1998, Sia *et al.* 2002). For instance, Sia *et al.* (2002) state that "the process oriented design not only drives the standardisation of processes, but also creates tighter interdependency across functional tasks, forcing hand off issues among peers to surface" (Sia *et al.* 2002, p. 25, also refer to Spears and Lea 1994).

Past researchers (e.g. Gattiker and Goodhue 2005, Shang and Seddon 2002) have investigated the overall impact of ERP on organisational performance. For instance, Knox *et al.* (2007) suggest one of the features of ERP as "the use of ERP streamlines and prevents duplication of activities, generates more information about the organisation in order to be able

to 'see' what different parts of the organisation are doing and therefore to 'know' the organisation across multiple lines of sight (p.28). However, this suggestion also implies that subsequent to the implementation, there would be considerable impact on individuals. However, past empirical research seldom addressed ERP's post-implementation impact from system end-users' perspective.

2.3 User groups and differing views on enterprise systems

2.3.1 User groups. User perspective is an important design consideration in information system evaluation (Gable *et al.* 2008). Different user groups have multiple and often conflicting objectives and priorities; they can have differing experience of the system (see Gable *et al.* 2008, Sedera *et al.* 2004). Therefore, extant literature highlights the importance of analysing user perspective at multiple levels within an organisation (e.g. Gable *et al.* 2003, Leider and Elam 1994, Sedera *et al.* 2004, Yoon and Guimaraes 1995).

Anthony (1965) identified three levels of management activities that occur in organisations: operational control, management control, and strategic planning. Operational control is the process of assuring that specific tasks are carried out effectively and efficiently; management control is the process by which managers assure that resources are obtained and used effectively and efficiently in the accomplishment of an organisation's objectives; strategic planning is the process of deciding objectives of an organisation, resources required to achieve these objectives, and policies that govern acquisition, use, and disposition of these resources. Based on Anthony's (1965) work, user groups can also be classified into operational, management and strategic. Operational level deals with real time data to carry out highly structured routine tasks which are governed by organisational rules and procedures. Management level deals with activities that are not repetitive but should be performed based on prescribed procedures. Strategic level deals with complex, irregular decision making and relies on predictive information for long term organisational goals. In addition to these three user groups, several scholars identified technical staff as a separate user group in information systems research (e.g. Doll *et al.* 1995; Sedera *et al.* 2006, Shang and Seddon 2000, 2002).

Overall, it is evident from extant information systems research that information required by each user group is different and it is important to gather views from different user groups when assessing enterprise systems.

Prior research generally gathered data from all or selected user groups discussed above depending on the particular research purpose. For instance, Sedera *et al.* (2006) and Ang and Soh (1997) gathered data from all user groups in a single study, Doll *et al.* (1995) and Guimaraes *et al.* (1996) gathered data from management, operational and technical user groups while Ifinedo and Nahar (2006) used strategic and management user groups. In our study, we gathered data from management and operational user groups. The demographic information of the sample is presented in section 3.1 (also refer to Table 1).

2.3.2 Deferring views on ERP product performance. Prior research provides evidence to differences in user perceptions towards product performance (e.g. Sedera *et al.* 2006; Singleton *et al.* 1988; Vlahos and Farrett 1995). For instance, Vlahos and Ferratt (1995) studied perceived value, use, and satisfaction levels across different user groups and found high level of satisfaction among technical support staff compared to other user groups. When assessing whether different user groups demonstrate different views on success dimensions, Sedera *et al.* (2004) noted that ease of use, ease of learning, and accessibility of the system did not report significant differences across strategic, management, operational, and technical users. However, they have observed significant differences in several other dimensions including accuracy of data, system flexibility, and system reliability, and highlighted the importance of gathering views from multiple stakeholders in evaluating success. Given the empirical and anecdotal evidence that indicate possible differences in perceptions towards product performance across different user groups, for this study, it is hypothesised:

Hypothesis 1: There will be significant perceptual differences between management and operational end-users on ERP system product performance.

2.3.3 Deferring views on post-implementation impact of ERP usage. Several researchers suggest that an enterprise system is not the driver of changes that occurred in an organisation, but integration, standardisation, routinisation, and centralisation that resulted from the implementation facilitate changes in organisations and individuals within those organisations (e.g. Arnold 2006, Morton and Hu 2008; Pinsonneault and Kraemer 1993, Scapens and Jazayeri 2003). On one hand, when users are seen as information transmitters they provide an information link between different user groups. For instance, management users, for the most part, provided an information link between strategic and operational users but the system would now perform these functions. The usage of ERP would permit strategic users to bypass management users in both upward and downward communication. It would also centralise organisation structures- horizontally by bringing business units together and vertically by bringing decision authority to the top of hierarchy (see Pinsonneault and Kraemer 1993). On the other hand, when users are seen as decision makers, richness of information provided by the system allows, for instance, management users to uncover details that were not previously known but are relevant in making decisions. Management users thus make more decisions and analyse more alternatives in greater depth than before (see Ellis 1984, Pinsonneault and Kraemer 1993). Consequently, overall result is a shorter, narrower hierarchy requiring far fewer management users. The management users who survived the organisational re-structuring process would be expected to shift in one of the two directions, i.e., a portion would see their jobs become more structured and routine, and sink into the operational level of organisations, while other portion would be promoted to strategic-level jobs requiring more creativity and control over a broader range of decisions (Pinsonneault and Kraemer 1993, 1997, see also Mann and Williams 1960).

Overall, when an enterprise system makes fundamental changes in the way an individual do his/her job, an outsider might observe that a mundane task has been transformed into a more enhanced, satisfying job. However, changes occurred after the implementation may not necessarily welcome by employees (see Arnold 2006). Over time, the affected employees might welcome changes, but alternatively may choose to change jobs, which can be very costly

to the organisation (Arnold 2006). However, extant literature suggests that changes subsequent to the implementation are not quite clear (see Arnold 2006). Therefore, for this study, we propose that post-implementation impact on individuals would differ depending on the user group they belong to, i.e., management or operational. Therefore, it is hypothesised:

Hypothesis 2: There will be significant perceptual differences between management and operational end-users on the impact of ERP system usage.

3. Research method

3.1. Measures

Unless otherwise stated, all constructs were measured on a five-point Likert response scale ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree). Where available, scale items from existing research were used. For the constructs that did not have readily available scale items, appropriate scale items were developed using guidelines recommended by Nunnally (1978). The measures used for the study are shown in Table 1. Standardised Cronbach's alpha of the scale was examined and principal-components factor analysis (Varimax rotation) was conducted. The criteria adhered to are: eigenvalues of all components should not be less than 1.0; the loadings should be 0.50 or greater to be considered practically significant; cronbach's alpha values of each factor extracted and overall measure should be greater than 0.7 (see Hair *et al.* 1998). The items of each factor were averaged to produce a mean score for the each construct (refer to Table 4).

ERP system product performance. The measure consisted of nine items and had a reliability of .769. Correlations of each item with the sum of scores on all items were taken into consideration and the two items "ERP provides easy access to needed information" and "ERP system is user friendly" were dropped to improve the reliability. The remaining 7-item measure (refer to Appendix D) retained a reliability of .802. As shown in Appendix D, factor analysis yielded one factor, where Eigenvalue=5.23; Explained variation=72%.

Impact of the ERP system usage. The measure consisted of 27 items and had a reliability of .745. Two items were dropped due to low item-to-total correlation, namely, “ERP system created and reinforced a sense of community across all units of the organisation” and “I have access rights for adequate information to carryout my work”. The remaining 25-item measure (refer to Appendix D) retained a reliability of .831. As shown in Appendix D, factor analysis yielded a set of seven factors, which explained 74 per cent (73.67) of the variance. Of these seven factors, Factor 1 was labelled as “Problem solving support”, Factor 2 as “Authority and decision rights”, Factor 3 as “Cross-functionality”, Factor 4 as “Job discretion”, Factor 5 as “Procedural formality”, Factor 6 as “Superior and peer visibility”, and Factor 7 as “Overall performance improvement”. The standardised estimates and reliability statistics for these factors are provided in Appendix D.

Respondents' level of participation in the ERP system and the degree of understanding of the ERP system were also explored. These two items were on a five-point Likert scale ranging from 1= very low to 5= very high.

3.2 Sample and data collection

The list of firms that implemented ERP systems was obtained from a firm that conducted a comprehensive market survey on ERP systems in use in Sri Lanka. The evaluation of the list suggested that the majority of firms belong to manufacturing sector has implemented ERP compared to any other sub sector belong to the industrial or service sector. In order to obtain a homogeneous sample of firms, we confined our sample to manufacturing firms that have implemented ERP systems. Appendix C provides readers a general idea about the industrial establishments operating in the country and number of persons engaged.

Sample selection was in two stages. First, a sample of private sector manufacturing firms was identified from the list that fulfilled the selection criteria set for the study, i.e., 1) business performance of the firms. Criteria such as revenue growth, return on assets, and growth of market share of the product segment, net profits, and profit to revenue ratio were

used and such information was obtained from published secondary data; and 2) the use of ERP system should be mandatory and it should be functioning for at least one year. About 20 firms fulfilled the criteria of which 15 firms willingly participated in this study.

As the second stage a contact person was identified from each firm. The contact person from each firm together with one of the authors of this paper identified end-users belong to management and operational level based on end-users' hierarchical level and the degree of involvement with business/work activities in his/her organisation (refer to Anthony, 1965), irrespective of job titles given by their employers. This measure was taken as different employers could have been given different job titles for similar nature of work in the manufacturing sector. Contact persons were instructed to distribute self-administered survey questionnaires to a randomly selected group of management and operational end-users throughout their organisations (from production, sales and distribution, HR, financial, etc. depending on the nature of modules implemented) (refer to Table 2). Participants were briefed the aims of the study prior to questionnaire distribution. Of the 300 questionnaires distributed, 100 management and 76 operational end-users responded. Five responses from management and four responses from operational end-users were excluded due to missing data, yielding 167 valid responses.

The profile of the firms and respondents are shown in Table 2. Over 88 percent of the respondents came from firms that employed more than 500 employees; 68 percent responded that more than 200 employees are using ERP in their firms. Therefore, though the Department of Census and Statistics (n.d.a) identifies manufacturing establishments with 10 person engaged as the lower bound for medium scale establishments (lower bound for large scale establishments is not specified), employee numbers in a particular firm in our sample are well above the lower bound of medium scale manufacturing establishments (refer to Table 2 and Appendix C).

Take in Table 2

The responses to management and operational end-users' level of usage of ERP and the degree of understanding of the system are shown in Table 3.

Take in Table 3

3.3 Methods of data analysis

Correlation analysis, independent sample t-test and logistic regression were used for the data analysis. User group was coded as management end-users=0 and operational end-users=1. For the logistic regression, management/operational end-users was taken as the dependent variable and the impact of the ERP system usage as independent variables. Forward stepwise Likelihood Ratio (LR) procedure was used to arrive at a final logistic regression model (see Hair *et al.* 1998). It should be noted that interrelationships between product performance dimensions and interrelationships between ERP usage dimensions are beyond the focus of this study and have not been explored as a result.

4. Results

Correlations of the variables by management and operational end-users are shown in Table 4. Correlations above the diagonal represent management end-users while correlations below the diagonal represent operational end-users.

Take in Table 4

The results of t-test examining differences between management and operational end-users' perceptions towards the product performance and impact of usage are shown in Table 5. There are no significant differences between the two groups in their perceptions towards ERP system product performance. Therefore, H1 is not supported.

Of the seven areas examined for the impact of ERP usage, three areas, i.e., problem solving support ($p < .05$), authority and decision rights ($p < .05$), and overall performance improvement ($p < .05$) showed significant differences. Management end-users rated the impact of usage on problem solving support and authority and decision rights relatively higher than operational end-users. Operational end-users rated the impact of usage on overall performance improvement relatively higher than management end-users. Therefore, H2 is partially supported.

Take in Table 5

The results of logistic regression are shown in Table 6. Nagelkerke R^2 was .837 suggesting that 84 per cent of the variance in the dependent variable is explained by the covariates. P -value of .765 of Hosmer and Lemeshow test ($.765 > .05$) suggested a good fit. The overall percentage of cases correctly classified is 73 (72.9%). The change in -2 Log-likelihood and their significance are also shown in Table 5. It is evident from Table 5 and Table 6 that problem solving support, authority and decision rights, and overall performance improvement are important post-implementation outcomes of the usage that discriminate between management and operational end-users. For instance, the odds of operational end-users to perceive higher level of overall performance improvement due to usage (as opposed to management end-users) is almost four times (3.75) as high. Overall, the results of logistics regression suggests that management end-users highly perceive the impact of usage on problem solving support and authority and decision rights while operational end-users highly perceive the overall performance improvement due to ERP.

Take in Table 6

5. Discussion and concluding remarks

This paper sought to illustrate the importance of assessing perceptions of management and operational end-users not only on ERP system product performance but also post-implementation impact of usage on individuals. Therefore, this article represents a progress towards enterprise system research that focused on perceptions towards ERP systems and issues associated with the usage resulting from fundamental changes in organisations. Investigating ERP system implementations in different regions of the world is important as multi-national organisations could use the information to gain the ability to successfully exchange business processes from one section of the organisation to the other. Therefore, it is expected that the findings presented in this paper would provide valuable information to both academics and practitioners. In addition, the findings of this study could serve to establish baseline data and would be a source of general guidance in stimulating a number of potentially significant future studies in this area.

The study inquired into the level of use and understanding of the system and did not find significant differences between management and operational end-users (refer to Table 2). When the use of a system is mandatory, the extent of use conveys little information about the system (see Robey 1979). Since the use is mandatory in the firms studied, this information is not taken into further analysis but taken to describe as a characteristic of the sample.

Drawing on previous research, the study investigated management and operational end-users' perceptions towards product performance based on information it produces (e.g. accuracy of output, reliability of output, and relevancy of output). The importance of gathering end-user perception towards these aspects has also been highlighted by Seddon (1997). Shang and Seddon (2000) suggested that management end-users are the most appropriate single user group from which to gather perceptions of enterprise system benefits. In our study, it was found that management and operational end-users' perceptions do not differ significantly on how they perceived the product performance. This finding supports the claims made by Sedera *et al.* (2004, 2006) that they have observed negligible differences between management and operational end-users in evaluating enterprise system performance. In this

regard, Gable *et al.* (2003) highlighted the importance of additivity of responses of different user groups in assessing the dimensions of enterprise systems. Therefore, there is a possibility to combine the views of management and operational end-users to gauge ERP system product performance. For instance, Sedera *et al.* (2004, 2006) having noted that management and operational user groups do not show significant perceptual differences of enterprise system dimensions, they have merged the two user groups into a single user group in evaluating enterprise system dimensions.

Drawing on previous research, the study investigated post-implementation impact of ERP usage on management and operational end-users. It was found that problem solving support, authority and decision rights, and overall performance improvement as important post-implementation outcomes of usage that discriminate between management and operational end-users. Operational end-users rated the impact of usage on overall performance improvement significantly higher than management end-users. Management end-users rated the impact of usage on problem solving support significantly higher than operational end-users. This supports previous studies that suggested the richness of information provided by the system allows management end-users to make more decisions and analyse more alternatives than before (e.g. Ellis 1984; Koh *et al.* 2008). Management end-users also rated the impact of usage on authority and decision rights significantly higher than operational end-users. When considering the aspects that were considered in exploring perceptions towards authority and decision rights (refer Appendix D) findings suggest that ERP has challenged management end-users' ability to own and control resources (including information) and their reluctance to share information with other people through the system. In short, management end-users could have perceived facilities provided by the system as a potential threat to their functional territoriality and as a way of reducing their organisational power. This supports previous studies that suggested centralised organisation structure facilitated by the ERP system would reduce decision authority of the management end-users (e.g. Pinsonneault and Kraemer 1993, 1997).

Overall, management and operational end-users do not show significant differences in their views towards the ERP system product performance. Yet, management and operational

end-users have been influenced differently. Hence, they have different views on problem solving support, authority and decision rights, and overall performance improvement facilitated by the system. Extant literature suggests the importance of additivity of respondents in assessing the dimensions of enterprise systems (e.g. Gable *et al.* 2003). The findings of our study also suggest the possibilities of combining views of both management and operational end-users in evaluating ERP system product performance. However, our findings show significant differences (in problem solving support, authority and decision rights, and overall performance improvement) between the two user groups in their perceptions towards post-implementation impact of ERP usage. This supports our proposition of canvassing views from different user groups as each user group has different and valuable views on how it affects them. Hence, the perceptions of different user groups have to be compared in a systematic way to arrive at an assessment of post-implementation impact on each user group. As we have not come across previous empirical studies that compared these aspects, this warrants future research. Finally, the insight given by the findings of our study would be beneficial to both academia and practice for the better understanding of ERP systems and impact of its usage on different user groups. The study also provides valuable information to firms that are either embarking on or considering ERP implementations to better prepare themselves for a successful post-implementation usage of the system.

6. Limitations and future research work

The study evaluated ERP systems based on the perceptions of end-users. Though Singleton *et al.* (1988) pointed out the need of assessing actual performance, measured internally, together with end-users' perceptions of the same service, actual data of product performance was left out due to difficulties in securing those from the participating organisations. The validity of a measure cannot be truly established on the basis of a single cross-sectional study. It requires the assessment of measurement properties over a variety of samples in similar and different contexts. Hence, future research, in different and larger samples and longitudinal studies, are necessary that compliment questionnaire surveys with

interviews. Specifically, explanatory research would be able to further the understanding of the perceptions of different user groups. From an organisational perspective, the presence of distinct frames of reference among people who work in different functional areas can lead to conflicting expectations and decrease productivity. Therefore, future studies could investigate the influence of differences between functional areas and personal cultural differences in the way work processes are interpreted even though there is some degree of cross-functional integration.

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Table 1 Measures and sources

Item	Source
ERP system product performance:	
ERP system provides reliable information.	Adapted from Ives <i>et al.</i> (1983), Sengupta and Zviran (1997), Doll and Torkzadeh (1988), Somer <i>et al.</i> (2003), Raymond (1987).
ERP system provides up-to-date information.	Adapted from Doll and Torkzadeh (1988) and Somer <i>et al.</i> (2003).
ERP system provides accurate information.	Adapted from Ives <i>et al.</i> (1983), Sengupta and Zviran (1997), Doll and Torkzadeh (1988), Somer <i>et al.</i> (2003), Raymond (1987).
ERP System is reliable.	Adapted from Calisir and Calisir (2004).
The information provided by the ERP system is very relevant to my job.	Adapted from Sengupta and Zviran (1997), Raymond (1987).
ERP System is fast and saves time.	Adapted from Doll and Torkzadeh (1988) and Somer <i>et al.</i> (2003).
The information provided by the ERP system is clear and understandable.	Adapted from Doll and Torkzadeh (1988) and Somer <i>et al.</i> (2003).
Post-implementation impact of ERP usage:	
ERP system provides me information which is useful in defining problems.	Adapted from Barki (1990).
ERP system provides me information which is useful in forming solutions.	Adapted from Barki (1990).
ERP system provides me information which is useful in selecting and prioritising problems.	Adapted from Barki (1990).
Increased control over operations gained through the ERP system helps me to make better decisions.	Developed for the current study.
I feel that other people do not ask for my expertise as information is readily available in the ERP system.	Adapted from Bradshaw-Cambali and Murray (1991).
I feel that my ability to own and control resources (including information) is challenged by the ERP system.	Adapted from Astley and Sachdeva (1984), Sillince and Mouakket (1997).
I like to share information with other people through the ERP system, if that improves their job performance.	Adapted from Astley and Sachdeva (1984), Sillince and Mouakket (1997).

I feel that my authority in transmitting information is reduced by the ERP system.	Adapted from Bradshaw-Cambali and Murray (1991).
I feel that with the ERP system, power resides not in people but in the system.	Adapted from Bloomfield and Coombs (1992).
As the ERP system provides a common platform for the organisation now I feel that we have a single system of reference.	Adapted from Lengnick-Hall and Lengnick-Hall (2006).
ERP system created opportunities for cross functional and cross occupational collaboration, learning and sharing experiences.	Adapted from Lengnick-Hall and Lengnick-Hall (2006).
With the use of the ERP system, it is very clear how my individual actions and outcomes affect the entire organisation.	Adapted from Lengnick-Hall and Lengnick-Hall (2006).
ERP system helps my department to synchronize with other departments.	Developed for the current study.
Because of the ERP system, I have considerable autonomy in deciding how to carry out my work.	Sia <i>et al.</i> (2002)
I feel my accountability for work has increased due to the use of the ERP system.	Developed for the current study.
Management relies a great deal on me to ensure proper operation/processing when I use the ERP system.	Sia <i>et al.</i> (2002).
The procedures to carry out a task are spelled out very clearly.	Sia <i>et al.</i> (2002).
Employees can be closely supervised to ensure that they are conforming to the standard procedures established.	Sia <i>et al.</i> (2002).
Standard procedures defined by the ERP system work as barriers when carrying out my day-to-day work.	Developed for the current study.
It is very convenient for my supervisor to access the ERP system to review my work performance.	Sia <i>et al.</i> (2002).
If there is an error, it is very easy for my supervisor to trace when, where, and by whom it was committed through the ERP system.	Sia <i>et al.</i> (2002).
If I do not perform my work, there is a great likelihood that other processes in the system can not proceed as they are dependent on my input.	Sia <i>et al.</i> (2002).
I am satisfied with the service the ERP system is doing for me and my work.	Developed for the current study.
The work processes in my organisation has improved after the ERP system implementation.	Adapted from Sia <i>et al.</i> (2002).
ERP system has had a significant positive effect on my organisation.	Gattiker and Goodhue (2005).
ERP system created and reinforced a sense of community across all units of the organisation.	Adapted from Lengnick-Hall and Lengnick-Hall (2006).
I have access rights for adequate information to carryout my work.	Developed for the current study.

Table 2
Demographic information (N=167)

<i>Industrial sector</i>		<i>Frequently implemented modules*</i>	
Export apparel manufacturing	57%	Material management	100%
Food, beverage and tobacco	23%	Production planning	100%
Plastic, rubber and polymer	10%	Financial accounting	98%
Other	10%	Sales and distribution	80%
		HR	42%
		Quality management	38%
		Maintenance	31%
<i>Number of employees in the firm</i>		<i>User group</i>	
Less than 500	12%	Management	57%
500 – 999	17%	Operational	43%
1,000 – 4,999	52%		
5,000 – 9,999	11%		
Above 10,000	8%		
<i>Number of employees using ERP</i>		<i>Gender</i>	
Less than 200	32%	Female	21%
200 – 500	48%	Male	79%
Above 500	20%		
<i>Product type</i>		<i>Respondents' age</i>	
Customised (developed for my firm)	31%	Less than 25 years	8%
Off-the-shelf with customisations	69%	25 – 29	34%
		30 – 34	42%
		Above 35	16%
<i>ERP use duration by the firm</i>		<i>Respondents' years of experience in the firm</i>	
Less than 3 years	30%	Less than 3 years	23%
3 - 5 years	41%	3 – 5 years	42%
More than 5 years	29%	More than 5 years	35%

Note: * percentages do not total into 100 due to multiple answers.

Table 3
Respondents' level of participation and understanding of the ERP system

	Management		Operational		t-test	
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	t	Sig (2 tailed)
Respondents' level of participation in (usage of) the ERP system	3.62	.97	3.81	.76	-1.05	.182
The degree of understanding of the ERP system	3.63	.86	3.55	.97	.33	.306

Table 4
Impact of ERP - correlations by user groups

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
1 End-user group	1							
2 Job discretion	-.029	1						
3 Procedural formality	-.071	.271*	1					
4 Superior and peer visibility	.020	.346**	.303*	1				
5 Problem solving support	-.475*	.392**	.286*	.317**	1			
6 Authority and decision rights	-.367*	-.134	-.132	-.333**	-.094	1		
7 Cross-functional integration	.164	.306**	.313**	.345**	.321**	-.304*	1	
8 Overall performance improvement	.527**	.385**	.181	.308**	.403**	-.079	.467**	1
9 ERP system product performance	.107	.549**	.328**	.558**	.512**	-.273*	.499**	.629**

* significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

** significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 5
ERP system product performance and impact of ERP usage

	Management		Operational		t-test	
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	t	Sig (2 tailed)
ERP system product performance	3.67	.75	3.83	.65	-.98	.326
<i>Impact of ERP usage:</i>						
Job discretion	3.48	.77	3.43	.76	.26	.794
Procedural formality	3.75	.75	3.65	.61	.65	.514
Superior and peer visibility	3.67	.79	3.69	.67	-.18	.855
Problem solving support	3.92	.51	3.62	.66	.69	.042*
Authority and decision rights	3.48	.71	3.17	.60	2.12	.036*
Cross-functional integration	3.81	.72	4.00	.46	-1.34	.187
Overall performance improvement	3.54	.97	3.95	.78	-2.13	.037*

Table 6
Summarised results of logistic regression - impact of ERP usage

	Coefficient	S.E.	Wald	P-value	Odds Ratio	Δ -2 Log-likelihood	Significance of change
Problem solving support	-1.134*	.628	5.21	.022	.238	6.34	.012*
Authority and decision rights	-.728*	.422	2.98	.045	.483	3.16	.047*
Overall performance improvement	1.323**	.437	9.18	.002	3.754	11.41	.001**
Constant	3.330	1.87	3.15	.076	27.935	-	-

Note: *: p<.05; **: p<.01; ***: p<.001.

Appendix

Appendix A: ERP system product performance measures mentioned in literature

Author(s)	Measure Timelines of output	Relevancy of output	Accuracy of output	Reliability of output	Precision of output	Completeness of output	Response time/saves time	Clarity- output format	Convenience access to information
Doll and Torkzadeh (1988)	√	√	√	√					
Ives <i>et al.</i> (1983)		√	√		√	√			
Sengupta and Zviran (1997)		√	√	√	√	√			
Somers <i>et al.</i> (2003)	√	√	√	√				√	
Wu and Wang (2006)	√	√	√	√		√	√	√	√

Appendix B: Post-implementation impact of ERP mentioned in literature

Authors	Impact	Decision making/ problem solving	Power/ authority/ resource control	Job discretion/ procedural formality	Superior visibility/ peer visibility/ system tracking capability	Cross- functionality/ cross- functional integration	Overall performance/ overall impact
Astley and Sachdeva (1984)			√				
Bendoly <i>et al.</i> (2006)						√	
Bloomfield and Coombs (1992)			√				
Bradshaw-Camball and Murray (1991)			√				
El Amrani <i>et al.</i> (2006)						√	
Gattiker and Goodhue (2005)		√				√	√
Goodhue <i>et al.</i> (1992)						√	
Jaspersen <i>et al.</i> (2002)			√				
Knox <i>et al.</i> (2007)		√	√				
Lengnick-Hall and Lengnick-Hall (2006)						√	
Scapens and Jazayeri (2003)				√			
Sewell (1998)					√		
Shang and Seddon (2002)		√					√
Sia <i>et al.</i> (2002)				√	√		√
Spears and Lea (1994)					√		
Spreitzer (1995)				√			
Wilson (1995)					√		
Wu and Wang (2006)		√					

Appendix C: Industrial establishments and number of persons engaged (as at the year 2004)

Major divisions	Number of establishments [†]					Number of persons engaged ^{††}				
	Total	Small industries [‡]		Medium and large industries ^{‡‡}		Total	Small industries [‡]		Medium and large industries ^{‡‡}	
	F	F	%	F	%	F	F	%	F	%
Mining and Quarrying	6,248	5,413	4.5	835	8.4	36,948	21,378	7.5	15,570	2.1
Manufacturing[◊]	124,351	115,351	95.0	9,000	90.3	990,348	262,716	92.0	727,632	97.3
Electricity, Gas and Water	788	657	0.5	131	1.3	6,155	1,453	0.5	4,702	0.6
Total	131,387	121,421	100	9,966	100	1,033,451	285,547	100	747,904	100

Manufacturing industry [◊]					
Persons engaged size class ^{††}	Establishments [†]		Persons engaged ^{††}		
	F	%	F	%	
Small industries [‡]	1-4	104,046	83.7	192,859	19.5
	5-9	11,305	9.1	69,859	7.1
	Subtotal	115,351	-	262,716	-
Medium and large industries ^{‡‡}	10-19	4,316	3.5	55,676	5.6
	20-49	2,239	1.8	66,270	6.7
	50-99	1,043	0.8	69,986	7.1
	100 and above	1,402	1.1	535,700	54.1
	Subtotal	9,000	-	727,632	-
Total	124,351	100	990,348	100	

Notes: F= Frequency; %= Percentage

[†] Establishment characteristics- Availability of its own production facilities; maintaining of accounts pertaining to the establishment; and availability of distinct management and a suitable location.

^{††} Number of persons engaged includes working proprietors, active partners, unpaid family workers, operatives and all other employees.

[‡] Less than 10 persons engaged

^{‡‡} 10 and more persons engaged.

[◊] Manufacturing establishment: Conversion of something or part into another by using chemical or mechanical process. This can be done by machines or labour force.

Source: Department of Census and Statistics of Sri Lanka (n.d.a)

Appendix D: Item measures and factor analysis diagnostics

ERP system product performance	
ERP system provides reliable information	.852
ERP system provides up-to-date information	.823
ERP system provides accurate information	.785
ERP System is reliable	.749
The information provided by the ERP system is very relevant to my job	.611
ERP System is fast and saves time	.602
The information provided by the ERP system is clear and understandable	.597
Explained variation	72.01%
Eigenvalue	5.23
Standardised Cronbach's alpha	.802
Post-implementation impact of ERP usage	
<i>Factor 1: Problem solving support</i>	
ERP system provides me information which is useful in defining problems	.833
ERP system provides me information which is useful in forming solutions	.819
ERP system provides me information which is useful in selecting and prioritising problems	.788
Increased control over operations gained through the ERP system helps me to make better decisions	.773
Explained variation	30.21%
Eigenvalue	8.16
Standardised Cronbach's alpha	.817
<i>Factor 2: Authority and decision rights</i>	
I feel that other people do not ask for my expertise as information is readily available in the ERP system (R)	.772
I feel that my ability to own and control resources (including information) is challenged by the ERP system (R)	.724
I like to share information with other people through the ERP system, if that improves their job performance	.711
I feel that my authority in transmitting information is reduced by the ERP system (R)	.658
I feel that with the ERP system, power resides not in people but in the system (R)	.623
Explained variation	11.70%
Eigenvalue	3.16
Standardised Cronbach's alpha	.723
<i>Factor 3: Cross-functionality</i>	
As the ERP system provides a common platform for the organisation now I feel that we have a single system of reference	.792
ERP system created opportunities for cross functional and cross occupational collaboration, learning and sharing experiences	.760
With the use of the ERP system, it is very clear how my individual actions and outcomes affect the entire organisation	.745
ERP system helps my department to synchronize with other departments	.684
Explained variation	8.92%
Eigenvalue	1.87
Standardised Cronbach's alpha	.792
<i>Factor 4: Job discretion</i>	
Because of the ERP system, I have considerable autonomy in deciding how to carry out my work	.780
I feel my accountability for work has increased due to the use of the ERP system	.728
Management relies a great deal on me to ensure proper operation/processing when I use the ERP system	.643
Explained variation	7.17%
Eigenvalue	1.66
Standardised Cronbach's alpha	.714

<i>Factor 5: Procedural formality</i>	
The procedures to carry out a task are spelled out very clearly	.857
Employees can be closely supervised to ensure that they are conforming to the standard procedures established	.832
Standard procedures defined by the ERP system work as barriers when carrying out my day-to-day work (R)	.721
Explained variation	5.81%
Eigenvalue	1.46
Standardised Cronbach's alpha	.798
<i>Factor 6: Superior and peer visibility</i>	
It is very convenient for my supervisor to access the ERP system to review my work performance	.833
If there is an error, it is very easy for my supervisor to trace when, where, and by whom it was committed through the ERP system	.763
If I do not perform my work, there is a great likelihood that other processes in the system can not proceed as they are dependent on my input	.672
Explained variation	5.19%
Eigenvalue	1.30
Standardised Cronbach's alpha	.728
<i>Factor 7: Overall performance improvement</i>	
I am satisfied with the service the ERP system is doing for me and my work	.923
The work processes in my organisation has improved after the ERP system implementation	.902
ERP system has had a significant positive effect on my organisation	.876
Explained variation	4.67%
Eigenvalue	1.16
Standardised Cronbach's alpha	.883

Note: "R" denotes reverse coded items.